

MEDICAL SCIENCES

FEATURES OF REHABILITATION MEASURES FOR MILITARY PERSONNEL WITH LOWER LIMB NERVE INJURIES

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ABSTRACT

Rehabilitation for military personnel with lower limb injuries is indeed a crucial component of an integrated medical support system. It encompasses physical, psychological, and social aspects to achieve the highest possible level of functionality and improve the quality of life for military personnel with lower limb injuries.

Keywords: rehabilitation, nerve damage, lower limbs, military personnel.

Key aspects of rehabilitation in this context include:

Medical Assistance and Surgical Treatment:

The initial stage of rehabilitation involves medical treatment to manage injuries and surgical interventions to restore the structural elements of the lower limbs.

Physiotherapy and Orthopedic Rehabilitation:

This aspect includes exercises to restore musculoskeletal function, strengthen muscles, improve mobility, and ensure optimal functional use of the lower limbs.

Psychological Support: Injuries to the lower limbs can impact the mental well-being of military personnel. Psychological support and counseling are essential elements of rehabilitation to help overcome stress, depression, and adaptation to new living conditions.

Professional Rehabilitation and Skills Assessment: Considering the unique nature of military service, it is important to provide opportunities for assessing and developing professional skills that align with the physical capabilities of military personnel.

Social Integration and Support: Rehabilitation also involves measures to enhance the social adaptation of military personnel, taking into account their personal, familial, and professional aspects.

The successful implementation of rehabilitation requires collaboration among various professionals such as physicians, physiotherapists, psychologists, social workers, and others. This collaboration aims to ensure an individualized approach and complete restoration of functionality for military personnel.

Relevance of the Problem

The frequency of armed conflicts, wars, and terrorist acts has become a common and persistent phenomenon in recent times. Every day, dozens of Ukrainians sustain severe injuries due to the ongoing war, with many military personnel and civilians being admitted to medical facilities with injuries to the lower limbs. The modern weaponry used in full-scale wars is highly destructive, and firearm injuries in combat zones have become widespread. Injuries to the nervous system pose a significant medical and social problem, affecting individuals' livelihoods and potentially leading to disability.

It has been observed that individuals with limb injuries resulting from modern combat operations, who received assistance at the tactical and early hospital stages, exhibit distinctive clinical-epidemiological and

clinical-nosological characteristics. The majority of these individuals are males of working age, ranging from 20 to 50 years old, constituting 88.85% of all affected individuals. This poses a significant issue both in the medical-social and economic spheres for the country as a whole. Analyzing the distribution of the affected individuals in terms of direct participation in combat indicates that 98.10% of the affected individuals belong to military formations. Concerning the integrated distribution of the mass by military rank, the data reveals that 64.36% of the affected individuals held military ranks below warrant officers and midshipmen, with 48.17% being soldiers. Data analysis of those affected by modern combat operations indicates that limbs are most frequently injured, accounting for 50.40% of cases. The majority of limb injuries are attributed to the lower limbs (62.02%), which is logical considering the impact of modern weaponry in contemporary combat conditions. Age distribution data indicates that 35.25% of the affected individuals were aged 20 to 30, and 34.26% were aged 30 to 40. People aged 20-40 make up almost 70% of the total population. The age group of 40-50 represents 19.42%. An interesting trend is that in the age group of 50+, injuries are more prevalent in women, with the prevalence index being in the age groups of 18-20 and 40-50 years [1].

Analysis of scientific information sources during the Anti-Terrorist Operation/Operation of United Forces (ATO/OOS) showed that in the structure of surgical losses, individuals with limb injuries accounted for 56.7–62.6%, either penetrating or isolated in nature. Clinical-epidemiological and clinical-anatomical studies have proven that individuals with shrapnel limb injuries make up 80.4%, with gunshot injuries at 13.1%, mine-explosive injuries at 2.2%, and explosive traumas at 4.3%. Shrapnel limb injuries are blind, isolated, or multiple in 70.6% of cases. Gunshot injuries are transverse in 75.8% and isolated in nature.

As of today, according to the United Nations, 8,173 Ukrainian civilians have died, and 13,620 have been injured during the ongoing war. Among the deceased, 3,600 were men, 2,100 were women, and nearly 500 were children. The primary cause of death for the majority of civilians (94%) was explosive weapons with a large area of effect. Another 6% died due to landmines and explosive objects [2].

Neurorehabilitation is currently one of the promising directions in modern medicine. It goes beyond

clinical neurology, considering not only the state of the nervous system in various neurological diseases but also the altered functional capabilities of individuals with these diseases.

Various specialists from different fields, including neurologists, physical exercise specialists, physiotherapists, reflexologists, psychologists, and social workers, are involved in the process of restoring impaired functions in nervous system diseases. Modern rehabilitative medicine combines traditional physical rehabilitation with the use of modern technologies.

Physical rehabilitation holds a significant place in the rehabilitation of individuals with nerve injuries to the lower limbs. It is applied in both professional and social rehabilitation as a therapeutic and preventive measure. The goal of using this means is the comprehensive restoration of physical condition and work capacity. The forms of using this rehabilitation tool include physical activity and natural factors.

Specially selected exercises are capable of restoring optimal mobility and balance of nervous processes, improving regulatory properties, activating the activity of endocrine glands, and stimulating vegetative functions and metabolic processes through motor-visceral reflex mechanisms. Physical rehabilitation is an integral part of medical rehabilitation used at any age and stage. The prescription, execution order of exercises, and forms and methods of application depend on the course of the disease, the patient's general condition, as well as the duration and stage of rehabilitation, and the mode of movement, etc [3].

It is important to note that the effectiveness of rehabilitation can significantly depend on the specific type and degree of nerve damage, as well as the individual characteristics of the patient. The rehabilitation plan must be individualized and developed by specialized medical personnel.

This issue underscores the importance of rehabilitation measures for nerve injuries to the lower limbs during combat operations. This requires early diagnosis, improvement in quality of life, and the provision of physiotherapy services to restore lost functions.

Research Objective:

The aim of the study is to determine the effectiveness of physical exercises and develop rehabilitation programs based on the severity of nerve injuries to the lower limbs in military personnel.

Research Tasks:

1. Analyze scientific and medical literature describing the application of physical rehabilitation in cases of lower limb nerve injuries.
2. Explain the anatomical-physiological structure of the peripheral nervous system, the mechanism of lower limb nerve injury, etiology, and pathogenesis.

3. Determine the clinical-epidemiological characteristics of lower limb nerve injuries during modern combat operations.

4. Characterize the symptoms and complications of lower limb nerve injuries.

5. Provide examples of different diagnostic methods for lower limb nerves.

6. Develop rehabilitation programs based on the severity of the injury.

7. Investigate the effectiveness of different rehabilitation programs for lower limb nerve injuries.

Research Object: Modern methods and various means of rehabilitation for lower limb nerve injuries in military personnel.

Research Subject: The effectiveness of physical rehabilitation on the restoration of functions in lower limb nerve injuries.

Research Methods: Analysis and synthesis of scientific literature on peripheral nervous system injuries, clinical manifestations, and symptoms of injuries. Teaching methods (questionnaires, interviews, consultations, observations), medical-biological methods (life history, complaints, tests, examinations).

Hypothesis: It is expected that the use of modern methods of physical rehabilitation, exercises, and physiotherapy procedures will improve the patient's condition and quality of life.

Practical Significance: The materials presented in the study can be utilized in the physical rehabilitation of individuals with lower limb injuries and nerve damage at different stages of treatment.

Scientific Novelty: The novelty lies in the comprehensive identification and analysis of the clinical-nosological structure of individuals with lower limb injuries during combat operations to form diagnostic and therapeutic tactics for restoring the body's functional capabilities. A rehabilitation program has been developed for those affected in modern military conditions with lower limb nerve injuries, utilizing a multidisciplinary approach and modern physical therapy methods.

Materials and Methods:

Patients from Ternopil Municipal Hospital No.3 were included in the examination. Pain assessment was conducted using the Visual Analog Scale (VAS). The VAS allows determining pain intensity on a strip of 10 cm, where 0-1 cm represents extremely weak pain, 2-4 cm is mild, 4-6 cm is moderate, 6-8 cm is very strong, and 8-10 points indicate unbearable pain. (Fig. 1)

A drawback of this scale is its unidimensionality. This scale only captures the intensity of pain, while the emotional component of the pain syndrome introduces significant errors into the VAS indicator.

Рис. Візуальна аналогова шкала оцінки інтенсивності болю

Figure 1. Visual Analog Scale for Pain

Measurements of the circumference of the lower limbs were taken to assess the difference in muscle tone between the affected and healthy limbs. This measure allowed identifying changes in limb volume, detecting swelling, atrophy, or hypertrophy of muscle fibers. Muscle tone in both legs was assessed. This evaluation was performed by palpation, allowing the determination of the tenderness and consistency of a specific muscle, its involvement in movement, as well as the identification of fibrillations and fasciculations in tissues. Manual muscle testing according to Lovett's scale was conducted. The results of this scale have the following interpretations: 0 = complete absence of muscle tension; 1 = traces of tension, meaning tension without movement; 2 = pronounced muscle tension and the ability to perform movement without the assistance of a rehabilitation specialist, without resisting force; 3 = complete range of motion against resistance; 4 = complete range of motion with moderate resistance throughout; 5 = complete range of motion with maximum resistance. To gather more information about the specific type of injury, tendon reflexes were examined, including:

1. Patellar reflex (occurs when tapping the patellar ligament below the kneecap. The subject sits on a chair, placing the legs so that the shins are at a right angle to the thighs, and the soles touch the floor. Another method is having the subject sit on a chair and cross one leg over the other). The reflex involves the contraction of the quadriceps femoris muscle and leg extension at the knee joint. Components of the reflex arc: femoral nerve, III and IV lumbar segments of the spinal cord.

2. Achilles reflex (elicited by tapping the Achilles tendon. The examination can be performed by having the subject kneel on a couch or chair so that the feet hang freely, and the hands rest against the wall or the back of the chair). The reaction involves plantar flexion of the foot. Components of the reflex arc: tibial nerve, I-II sacral segments of the spinal cord.

Bohannon Test allows assessing the patient's balance in a standing position, which is necessary during walking. The test involves a gradual reduction of the support base and the duration of staying in this position (Table 1).

Table 1.

Balance assessment in a standing position according to Bohannon

Mark	Score Test Description
0	Unable to stand
1	Can maintain balance for less than 30 seconds with feet shoulder-width apart
2	Can maintain balance for more than 30 seconds with feet shoulder-width apart. Unable to stand with feet together.
3	Can stand with feet together for less than 30 seconds
4	Stands with feet together for 30 seconds and more

Tactile sensitivity was checked using cotton (a soft brush or a piece of paper can also be used). Gentle touches were applied to the skin on the healthy and affected sides, with the patient's eyes closed.

Methods for assessing the functional state of the body

The main indicators of the functional state are respiratory rate, heart rate, blood pressure, and body temperature. Each of these indicators has its physiological and age-related norms, and pathological deviations lead to specific symptoms. The overall assessment of a person's health cannot be made without knowing all physiological and pathological indicators.

Arterial blood pressure (BP) is a physiological value, so it constantly changes under the influence of various factors: age, time of day, emotional state, physical activity, meal intake, medication use, and interaction with a doctor. Even in people without health problems, blood pressure levels fluctuate throughout the day [4].

Normal blood pressure values range from 110 to 139 mmHg for systolic blood pressure and from 70 to 85-89 mmHg for diastolic blood pressure. Pressure below these limits is considered hypotension, and above them is hypertension. Hypertension is further divided into borderline (140-159 / 86-90 mmHg) and true

(160/90 mmHg and above). Persistent low blood pressure is called hypotension, and persistent high blood pressure is called hypertension. Throughout the day, arterial blood pressure fluctuates depending on the phase of the cardiac cycle. Blood pressure can also change due to stress, physical exertion, and the intake of a large amount of fluid, so it is necessary to measure blood pressure when selecting physical activity in people who have undergone amputation of the lower limb at the calf level [5].

The body's reaction to the loads is determined during the exercises by external signs, behavior, well-being, and the level of performance of individuals engaged in physical activities. It is worth noting that relying on the subjective assessment of the load can sometimes be inadequate and lead to negative shifts due to people overestimating their abilities. Therefore, when monitoring the intensity and permissibility of the load, it is necessary to focus on heart rate (HR). For this purpose, the HR level is determined before the session, in the main part, and at the end of the final part. The permissible value is 150 for those aged 40-49, 140 for those aged 50-59, and 130 for those aged 60 and older per minute [6].

Research Results

According to the data, all respondents were in the eastern territories of our country and sustained injuries while performing combat missions. The research results indicate that pain syndrome was identified in all 11 patients (100%). Based on the nature of the injuries, gunshot wounds were found in 4 individuals (36.4%), shrapnel injuries in 3 (27.3%), and mine-explosive injuries in 4 (36.4%). Regarding the localization of the injuries, they were divided into: thigh injuries in 2 military personnel (18.2%), shin injuries in 5 (45.5%), and foot injuries in 4 (36.4%). In 2 individuals (18.2%), damage to the femoral nerve was detected, accompanied by a loss of knee reflex and impaired sensitivity on the anterior surface of the thigh. Among the examined, there are also 3 military personnel (27.3%) with damage to the sciatic nerve, accompanied by a loss of Achilles reflex and sensory disturbances on the posterior surface of the shin. Additionally, 2 individuals (18.2%) were identified with injuries to the tibial nerve, resulting in impaired sensitivity on the outer surface of the shin and the dorsal surface of the foot. By conducting calculations, it can be concluded that sensory disturbances were identified in 7 subjects (63.6%).

Conclusion

Physical rehabilitation proves to be not only an effective means of treatment but also a crucial stage in social rehabilitation, aimed at returning the patient to active life and society. Specifically tailored exercises

contribute to the restoration of mobility, balance, and the activation of the body's regulatory properties.

This issue underscores the importance of rehabilitation measures in cases of nerve damage to the lower extremities during military actions. This calls for prompt diagnosis and the provision of physical therapy services to improve functionality and restore lost functions.

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